

ON THE BASE EXCHANGE POWER OF CLAY MINERALS*

BY S. N. BAGCHI

The most important and characteristic property of clays is their base exchange capacity (b.e.c.). As the clay minerals are the dominant constituents of clays, their base exchange capacity is rightly attributed to these clay minerals.

Four groups of clay minerals have been distinguished. These are (1) the kaoline group having the chemical composition $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{SiO}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$; (2) the montmorillonite group derived from the ideal formula $(\text{Al}_3)(\text{Si}_4)\text{O}_{10}(\text{OH})_2$ of pyrophyllite; (3) the illite group or the hydrous micas differentiated from muscovite mica, $\text{K}(\text{Al}_2)(\text{AlSi}_3)\text{O}_{10}(\text{OH})_2$, by their relatively small content of potassium and large percentage of water, and (4) the attapulgite group having the composition $(\text{OH}_2)_4(\text{OH})_2\text{Mg}_3\text{Si}_8\text{O}_{30} \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

The table below gives the values of b. e. c.'s of these clay minerals as compiled by Grim (*J. Geol.*, 1942, 50, 225).

TABLE I

B. e. c. (m. e.) per 100 g.

Kaolinite	3-15	Attapulgite	25-30
Montmorillonite	60-100	Illite	20-40

All of these minerals, however, possess the same general scheme of atomic structure (cf Pauling, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.*, 1930, 16, 123). This consists of fused sheets of tetrahedral silica and octahedral hydrargillite (or brucite). Kaolinite is built up of unsymmetrical packets consisting of one sheet of tetrahedral silica fused to a sheet of octahedral hydrargillite. In montmorillonite the two sides of the octahedral layer are attached to two tetrahedral layers. But Al^{+++} and Si^{++++} , which are the only cations (leaving aside H^+ ions of OH groups) contained in these ideal structures, are not the usual exchangeable bases of clays. How do these exchangeable bases come in? Why the b.e.c. of montmorillonite differs so widely from that of kaolinite? A correct answer to the first question seems to satisfy the second one too.

Naturally occurring montmorillonites contain a large amount of cations other than Al^{+++} and Si^{++++} . Kaolinite, however, is practically free from them.

* Submitted at a symposium on base exchange of clays, held at Delhi Session of Indian Science Congress in January 1947.

has rightly been suggested that during the growth of the crystals isomorphous replacements within the lattice takes place and in order to balance the charge excess cations are held within the lattice (Hendricks, *J. Geol.*, 1942, 50, 276).

From dimensional considerations it appears very probable that the unsymmetrical structure of kaolinite would not be able to bear the strain of incorporation of cations other than Si^{++++} and Al^{+++} within the lattice (cf. Pauling, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.*, 1930, 16, 578). Actually we find almost a complete lack of isomorphous replacement in these minerals. And consequently there could be no mono- or bivalent cations like those encountered in montmorillonites.

The work of Marshall (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1930, 26, 173 ; *Z. Krist.*, 1935, 91, 431), Nagelschmidt (*Min. Mag.*, 1938, 25, 140), Hendricks *et al.*, (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 1457 ; *Soil. Sci.*, 1943, 56, 285) and Giesking (*Soil Sci.*, 1939, 47, 1) have definitely shown that exchangeable bases are the integral constituents of the lattice. Moreover, in montmorillonites they are just those cations which have been incorporated into the lattice as a result of these isomorphous replacements. A more direct evidence of this hypothesis, viz., that the 'excess cations' are the usual exchangeable bases, is furnished by feldspars and zeolites whose atomic structures are more thoroughly known.

But kaolinite, as has already been pointed out, contains practically no mono- or bivalent cations. To what is then its b.e.c. due? Opinion in this case differs. Hendricks (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1945, 37, 625) recently suggested that the base exchange power of kaolinitic minerals is due to the unsatisfied valencies developed as a result of lattice termination. The cations are fixed up by the negative ends of the broken bonds of these ionic lattices. It is to be noted that in order to satisfy 'microscopic neutrality' of the individual crystallites, whenever a negative end arises simultaneously there appears a positive end which ought to take up anions. This amphoteric character of broken bonds has recently been stressed by Mitra (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 23, 386). But if the broken bonds are responsible for the base exchange power of kaolinite, it is expected that they should also play their part in the case of other ionic lattices. The accumulated evidences on montmorillonites, feldspar and zeolites, however, show, as has already been pointed out, that it is the 'excess cations' of the lattice, and not those fixed by broken bonds (if fixed at all), which are responsible for their base exchange power.

It is more probable that H^+ ions of OH groups of kaolinite lattice are responsible for its b.e.c., as has been suggested by Kelley and his co-workers (*Soil Sci.*, 1936, 41, 367). On this basis a plausible explanation is found for the dibasic acid character of hydrogen kaolinite as observed by Mukherjee and co-workers (*Ind. J. Agric. Sci.*, 1942, 12, 889). In kaolinite which has a polar structure, two crystallographically different types of OH groups exist. The exposed OH groups are expected to be more basic and show a greater resemblance with those of pure $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$ than the subsurface OH groups

whose greater acid character can be traced to their location in a more acidic environment arising from a bonding of the basic alumina to acidic silica. The two types of OH groups will have different bonding energies and different degrees of dissociation. Hydrogen ions in two affinity levels are thus expected and these would be responsible for the observed dibasic acid character.

The question naturally arises what part the OH groups of montmorillonite lattice play in the b.e.c. of this mineral? Why hydrogen montmorillonites show monobasic acid character? The b.e.c. due to OH group alone (if we accept the measure of kaolinite) is a small fraction (about 10%) of that of montmorillonite. That the OH groups of montmorillonite lattice can play their part appears from the fact that its ideal structure, pyrophyllite, which contains no mono- or bivalent cation, also possesses a definite but small b.e.c. comparable to kaolinite (Kelley *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). Hence, their contribution, if there be any, is perhaps overlooked. The b.e.c. of hydrogen montmorillonite is due mainly to the H^+ ions on the surface of the packets derived from an exchange of the balancing cations of the lattice. Being at a considerable distance from the centres of negative charges, these H^+ ions are expected to be more dissociable than the H^+ ions of the OH groups. Further, the first stage of dissociation involving the former category of H^+ ions will tend to suppress that of the hydroxylic hydrogens as in the case of polybasic acids. The observed monobasic acid character of hydrogen montmorillonite is therefore expected being due to a neutralisation of these readily dissociable H^+ ions. A second inflexion in the titration curve due to hydroxylic hydrogens, though not incompatible with structural considerations, is not observed, being too weak for detection as in the case of the third stage of dissociation of phosphoric acid (c.f. Britton, "Hydrogen Ions").

PHYSICAL CHEMISTRY LABORATORY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE,
CALCUTTA.

Received September 23, 1948.